

NONLINEAR FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF FIBRE COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT PROPERTIES IN TENSION AND COMPRESSION

J. Wang, and Y. Xiao*

School of Aerospace Engineering and Applied Mechanics, Tongji University,
Shanghai 200092, China

Email: y_xiao@tongji.edu.cn

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ABSTRACT

Recently authors developed a unified nonlinear constitutive model for predicting the tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves for fibrous composites. This study extended the constitutive model to that as a nonlinear finite element analysis tool. A user-defined material subroutine (UMAT) was written to address two- or three-dimensional finite elements in the finite element program ABAQUS. The proposed model was verified by performing numerical simulations of stress-strain curves for unidirectional and angle-ply laminates under tension and compression. Elastic-plastic stress analyses for cantilever laminated beam were discussed to illustrate the features of the unified nonlinear constitutive modeling methods that was implemented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibrous composites exhibit physical tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves under off-axis loadings. This characteristic is similar to the Baughinger effect that is usually observed for metallic materials. Tsai and Sun [1] interpreted this phenomenon as not only the pressure-dependent behavior of matrix but also the thermal residual stresses in both phases arising from different thermal expansion coefficients of fiber and matrix. Xiao et al [2] attributed this asymmetry in stress-strain curves to a comprehensive effect of thermal residual stresses, material deformations, and different mechanisms on damage and failure. Establishment of a functional constitutive model plays a crucial role in accurately describing the different nonlinear behavior and evaluating the strength, damage and durability of composite structures.

As increasingly used of finite element method to elastic-plastic mechanics, fracture mechanics and fluid mechanics, applications of the commercial finite element package in particular ABAQUS to deformation and stress analyses for optimal design of composite structures gradually become a tendency. By writing a user-defined material subroutine, users entitle to define their own constitutive models and write needed algorithms in ABAQUS. Norman [3-4] described different failure initiation criteria and material degradation models to define progressive failure formulations which were implemented in a user-defined material model for structural analysis of orthotropic bimodulus materials. Extensions of this user-defined material model to thermo-mechanical progressive failure analysis were also developed. Tabiei and Jiang [5] developed a generalized micromechanical model for two-dimensional extent of woven fabric with nonlinear stress-strain relations. This user-defined material model was suitable for implicit and could be modified for explicit finite element codes to deal with problems such as crashworthiness, impact, and failure analysis under static loads. Ding et al [6] proposed a three-dimensional thermo-viscoplastic model to simulate the residual stress in composite laminates during curing using the differential constitutive law by incorporating the corresponding differential finite element codes into ABAQUS with an UMAT subroutine.

Recently a nonlinear constitutive model was developed by authors [7-8] for fibrous composites with tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves, based on a generalized Hill yield criterion which combines Drucker-Prager yield criterion considering the effect of hydrostatic pressure and Hill yield criterion for anisotropic materials. In the present study, this model was extended to a three-dimensional form and implemented as a nonlinear finite element analysis tool in ABAQUS by writing a user-defined material subroutine. Numerical simulations of unidirectional and angle-ply composite laminates under tension and compression were compared with experimental data. Elastic-plastic stress

and deformation analyses of cantilever laminated beam were carried out to indicate the great differences in stress distribution and deformation response between Sun-Chen's one-parameter plasticity model (without strength-differential (NSD) effect) and the developed nonlinear constitutive model (with strength-differential (SD) effect).

2 ELASTIC-PLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

A three-dimensional nonlinear constitutive model capable of predicting the tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves for fibrous composites is established in this section. This simple model is extended as a new application of Sun and Chen's one-parameter plasticity model. A generalized Hill yield criterion is also given as the plastic potential function by combining the Drucker-Prager yield criterion which considers the effect of hydrostatic pressure for isotropic materials and Hill yield criterion suitable for anisotropic materials:

$$f^* = \sqrt{f_{\text{Hill}}^*(\sigma_{ij})} + K_1\sigma_{11} + K_2\sigma_{22} + K_3\sigma_{33} \quad (1)$$

where f_{Hill}^* is the Hill yield function for anisotropic materials as a function of the Cauchy stress tensor. K_1, K_2, K_3 stand for pressure-modified coefficients in the material principle directions. Thus the no-dimensional yield criterion can be expressed as:

$$f^* - 1 = 0 \quad (2)$$

Following the definition of effective stress, an equivalent form of the no-dimensional yield criterion is written as:

$$\bar{\sigma} - \bar{Y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where \bar{Y} refers to the average yield strength that is related to the tensile and compressive yield strengths in the material principle directions. $\bar{\sigma}$ is the effective stress which can be derived with the same assumptions in [7] that no plastic deformation in the fiber direction and transversely isotropy with the material symmetry in the 2-3 plane. Its three-dimensional form is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma} &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}\{(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + 4\sigma_{23}^2 + 2\Gamma^2 a_{66}(\sigma_{31}^2 + \sigma_{12}^2)\}} + \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}}(\Gamma - 1)(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \\ &= \bar{\sigma}_{3D} + \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}}(\Gamma - 1)(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

It is noticed that the various parameters in the generalized Hill yield criterion are widely simplified as two parameters in Equation (4). Compared to the one-parameter plasticity model, an additional parameter that indicates the ratio of compressive and tensile transverse yield strengths is incorporated to represent the yield strength-differential (SD) effect. When a plane stress state is considered, the effective stress in Equation (4) reduces to the two-dimensional form in [7].

The incremental plastic strains can be given using the associated flow rule:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \frac{\partial f^*}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} d\lambda \quad (5)$$

where $d\lambda$ is a proportionality factor.

Following the incremental approach of plastic work per unit volume, the relation between the incremental plastic strain and effective plastic strain is obtained:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} d\bar{\varepsilon}^p \quad (6)$$

Substitution of Equation (4) into Equation (6) yields

$$\begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{11}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{22}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{33}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{23}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{31}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{12}^p \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{3(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})}{2\bar{\sigma}_{3D}} + \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}}(\Gamma - 1) \\ \frac{3(\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{22})}{2\bar{\sigma}_{3D}} + \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}}(\Gamma - 1) \\ \frac{6\sigma_{23}}{\bar{\sigma}_{3D}} \\ \frac{3\Gamma^2 a_{66}\sigma_{31}}{\bar{\sigma}_{3D}} \\ \frac{3\Gamma^2 a_{66}\sigma_{12}}{\bar{\sigma}_{3D}} \end{Bmatrix} d\bar{\varepsilon}^p \quad (7)$$

A power hardening law is adopted for the effective stress and effective plastic strain

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^p = A\bar{\sigma}^n \quad (8)$$

where A and n are material plasticity parameters determined by experimental data.

The total strain increment is linearly decomposed into the elastic part and plastic part as

$$d\varepsilon_{ij} = d\varepsilon_{ij}^e + d\varepsilon_{ij}^p \quad (9)$$

The incremental elastic and plastic strains can also be presented with an incremental elastic-plastic constitutive equation in the following form:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij} = (S_{ijkl}^e + S_{ijkl}^p) d\sigma_{kl} \quad (10)$$

where S_{ijkl}^e and S_{ijkl}^p are respectively elastic and plastic compliance matrices.

The explicit form of elastic compliance matrix under two- or three-dimensional stress state can be fully determined by elastic theory for orthotropic materials. It is crucial to derive the explicit form of plastic compliance matrix for the incremental plastic constitutive equation. From Equation (10), we transform the implicit plastic compliance matrix into an explicit form using Equations (4), (7) and (8):

$$S_{ijkl}^p = \frac{d\varepsilon_{ij}^p}{d\sigma_{kl}} = \frac{d\varepsilon_{ij}^p}{d\bar{\varepsilon}^p} \frac{d\bar{\varepsilon}^p}{d\bar{\sigma}} \frac{d\bar{\sigma}}{d\sigma_{kl}} \quad (11)$$

Through some algebraic manipulations, the incremental form of elastic-plastic constitutive equation which considers the SD effect is given explicitly with a three-dimensional condition.

In order to conveniently incorporate the constitutive equations into finite element analysis tools, we defining a Jacobian matrix as the inverse of elastic-plastic compliance matrix:

$$J_{ep} = [S_{ijkl}^{ep}]^{-1} \quad (12)$$

3 NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION

A FORTRAN subroutine called UMAT has been written particularly for the finite element code ABAQUS for the developed three-dimensional constitutive model. When the subroutine is called by ABAQUS at each material integration point of the elements, it is provided with the state at the start of the increment (i.e., stresses, solution-dependent state variables) and the strain increments. The stresses and the solution-dependent state variables are then updated to their values with the corresponding numerical integration algorithms at the end of the increment. The material Jacobian matrix is also provided for the developed model. This implementation process includes several steps that are the elastic predictor, stress state recognition, yield judgement, stresses and strains update and Jacobian matrix calculation. Implementation details and the use of the subroutine are followed:

1. Call UMAT and input initial conditions at the start of the $n+1$ th increment.
2. Elastic predictor: calculate the trial stresses with elastic constitutive equation:
3. Stress state recognition (tension or compression):

$$\sigma_m = \frac{\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{3} \quad (13)$$

If $\sigma_m \geq 0$, the material is understood to be under tension; otherwise, it is under compression.

4. Yield judgment (generalized Hill yield criterion): substitute the current and trial stresses into Equation (3) respectively to judge whether the material yields. Three general conditions may occur in this step as described in the following step.
5. Stresses and strains update: for different general conditions in the yield judgement, corresponding integration algorithms are discussed to update the stresses and solution-dependent state variables.
 - a. Stage I: it is observed that there is no plastic strain at the end of $n+1$ th increment. Update the stresses with elastic constitutive equation.
 - b. Stage II: no plasticity appears at the start of the $n+1$ th increment but it exhibits at the end of the $n+1$ th increment. It means that the material begins to yield in the $n+1$ th increment. Considering the gradual yield of material in the stress-strain relation, the elastic constitutive equation is utilized to update the stresses for simplicity. This deviation can be controlled and reduced widely by setting a smaller increment size.
 - c. Stage III: plasticity exhibits at the start of the $n+1$ th increment and then gradually evolves. The stresses and solution-dependent state variables are updated using the yield criterion in Equation (3), the hardening power law in Equation (8), the associated plastic flow rule in Equation (6) and the constitutive matrix at the current increment:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{n+1} &= \sigma_n + J_{ep} : \Delta \varepsilon_{n+1} \\ d\bar{\sigma} &= \bar{\sigma}_{n+1} - \bar{\sigma}_n \\ d\bar{\varepsilon}^p &= d\bar{\sigma} / H_p \\ \varepsilon_{n+1}^p &= \varepsilon_n^p + \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}}{\partial \sigma_{n+1}} d\bar{\varepsilon}^p \\ \varepsilon_{n+1}^e &= \varepsilon_n^e + \Delta \varepsilon_{n+1} - \varepsilon_{n+1}^p \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

6. Calculate the Jacobian matrix and exit UMAT: provide the material Jacobian matrix to the main program at the end of the $n+1$ th increment. The updated stresses and solution-dependent state variables are stored in the STATEV and passed onto the UMAT at the beginning of the next increment.

The flow chart of this subroutine is shown in Figure 1.

4 NUMERICAL ANALYSES

To demonstrate the various features of this unified constitutive model implemented as a UMAT subroutine for predicting the tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves for fibrous composites, numerical simulations of unidirectional and angle-ply composite laminates under tension and compression were performed. Elastic-plastic stress analyses on composite laminate cantilever beam were carried out to indicate the great differences in stress distribution and deformation response between Sun-Chen's one-parameter plasticity model (NSD model) and the proposed nonlinear constitutive model (SD model).

4.1 Unidirectional and angle-ply laminates

Two groups of composite laminates fabricated from 12 plies of Toho Rayon IM600/Q133, a graphite/epoxy system were considered in this study. The rectangular laminates in these two groups had the following dimensions: length $L=200$ mm, width $W=20$ mm and thickness $T=1.8$ mm. Numerical simulations of four off-axis configurations (15° , 30° , 45° and 90°) from the first group and two angle-ply laminates ($[\pm 30^\circ]$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]$) from the second group were performed.

The unidirectional laminates and the angle-ply laminates are modelled using 8-node solid finite element C3D8R available within ABAQUS. Considering the asymmetry of the laminate, the whole laminate was simulated for finite element analysis regardless of the symmetry of its geometry and

loading. A schematic representation of the geometry, finite-element meshes and boundary conditions of these two finite element models are illustrated in Figure 2. The node at the center of the model is fully prevented from moving along the directions. Displacement-controlled tensile or compressive loading is applied to the loaded surfaces. 50 steps are set to control the increment size for reducing the deviation in stage II. The input model and material parameters for numerical simulation are shown in Table 1, which have been obtained from the off-axis tension and compression tests in [7]. An element at the center of the model is monitored for the purpose of comparison with experimental data.

Figure 1: The flow chart of the UMAT subroutine.

Figure 2: Geometry, finite-element meshes and boundary conditions of IM600/Q133 composite specimens: (a) geometry, (b) finite-element meshes and boundary conditions.

Model and material parameters	Tension	Compression
E_1 [GPa]	137.3	137.3
E_2 / E_3 [GPa]	8.9	8.9
G_{12} / G_{13} [GPa]	4.4	4.4
G_{23} [GPa]	3.0	3.0
ν_{12} / ν_{13} [GPa]	0.33	0.33
ν_{23} [GPa]	0.48	0.48
a_{66}	1.2	1.2
A [MPa ⁻ⁿ]	2.33e-12	2.09e-13
n	4.6	4.78
α	1.0	1.7

Table 1: Model and material parameters for IM600/Q133 composite.

The results of simulations for off-axis tension and compression tests on unidirectional laminates are shown in Figure 3. The FEM model predicted tension results for all fiber orientations agreed well with the experimental data, noting that the proposed model reduces to Sun-Chen's one-parameter plasticity model in tension. A good correlation between experimental and analytical curves in compression is also observed, with a maximum error of about 8% under 90° off-axis angle. Figure 4 shows the comparison of simulated stress-strain curves and experimental data on angle-ply laminates using the same parameters as the unidirectional laminates. For $[\pm 30^\circ]$ laminate, model predictions show good correlations with the experiment up to a strain value of 1% in tension and 1.5% in compression. For $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminate, the simulated results give a close fit to the experimental results with an error of about 7% at a maximum strain level of 5.5% in tension and an error of about 11% at a maximum strain level of 6% in compression. The present model demonstrates the potential to predict the tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves for fibrous composites on unidirectional and angle-ply laminates.

Figure 3: Comparison of predicted and measured stress-strain curves of unidirectional IM600/Q133 composites under off-axis loadings: (a) tension, (b) compression.

Figure 4: Comparison of predicted and measured stress-strain curves of angle-ply IM600/Q133 composite laminates under off-axis loadings: (a) tension, (b) compression.

4.2 Cantilever laminated beam

In this section, elastic-plastic stress and deformation analyses are carried out in a solid layers $[30^0 / -30^0 / 90^0]_s$ composite laminate cantilever beam as shown in Figure 5. The beam is loaded by a concentrate force opposite to the y direction at its free end. All the results are obtained from the finite element analyses with parameters in Table 1. Comparisons of stress distribution and deformation response in the beam between SD and NSD models are mainly discussed to illustrate the features of the unified nonlinear constitutive modeling methods that has been implemented.

Figure 5: Cantilever laminated beam.

Figure 6 shows the stress distributions of σ_x in all solid layers of the composite laminate cantilever beam with SD and NSD models at $P=10N$, presented in a same legend setting. For a given solid layer, the stresses exhibit asymmetry distributions in tensile and compressive regions. It is noticed that for each solid layer, the stress distributions between SD and NSD models are different. The difference is much little but exhibits apparently in regions where hold a higher stress. Figure 7 shows the stress distributions of $\bar{\sigma}$ in all solid layers of the beam with SD and NSD models at $P=10N$. It is observed that the effective stresses with NSD model are nearly symmetry in the tensile and compressive regions, while greatly asymmetry exhibits with SD model. Considering that the effective stress is an equivalent form of the no-dimensional yield criterion in equation (3), the regions marked in blue color indicate an elastic deformation state. Plasticity evolves in remain regions marked in red. Thus the differences in elastic or plastic regions are apparently observed.

Figure 6: The stress distributions of σ_x in all solid layers of the cantilever laminated beam at $P=10N$: (a) SD model; (b) NSD model.

Figure 7: The stress distributions of $\bar{\sigma}$ in all solid layers of the cantilever laminated beam at $P=10N$: (a) SD model; (b) NSD model.

Figure 8 shows the load-displacement curves of the cantilever beam with elastic, SD and NSD models. The displacement of the center point at the free end is monitored. It is observed that the load-displacement curve with elastic model is linear while other ones with SD and NSD models exhibit nonlinearity. The elastic model produces a higher stiffness than the elastic-plastic models (SD and NSD models). The NSD model generates a lower stiffness than SD model due to the more plastic flow in tension. The deviation between SD and NSD models begins to appear when the loading arrives at

25 N. Subsequently as the loading increases to 55 N, the deviation reaches up to 3.5%, which in a way can be never ignored for optimal design of composite structures.

Figure 8: The load-displacement curves of the composite laminate cantilever beam with elastic, SD and NSD models.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The developed two- or three-dimensional constitutive model for predicting the tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves for fibrous composites was extended to that as a nonlinear finite element analysis tool. A user-defined material subroutine was written to address two- or three-dimensional finite elements in the finite element program ABAQUS. Numerical simulations indicate great accuracy of the model in predicting the tension-compression asymmetry in stress-strain curves for unidirectional and angle-ply composite laminates. Elastic-plastic stress analyses for composite laminate cantilever beam were also discussed to illustrate the features of the unified nonlinear constitutive modeling methods that was implemented.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Tsai and C.T. Sun, Constitutive model for high strain rate response of polymeric composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **62**, 2002, pp. 1289-1297.
- [2] Y. Xiao, H. Hatta and M. Kawai, Observations on tensile and compressive behaviour for off-axis fibre composites, *Proceedings of the 10th Japan International SAMPE Symposium*, Tokyo, CD-ROM: PMC-7-5, 2007.
- [3] Norman F. Knight, Jr, User-defined material model for progressive failure analysis, *NASA/CR-214526*. Washington: NASA, 2006.
- [4] Norman F. Knight, Jr, User-defined material model for thermo-mechanical progressive failure analysis, *NASA/CR-215528*. Washington: NASA, 2008.
- [5] A. Tabiei and Y. Jiang, Woven fabric composite material model with material nonlinearity for nonlinear finite element simulation, *International Journal of Solids and structures*, **36**, 1999, pp. 2757-2771.
- [6] A.X. Ding, S.X. Li, J.H. Wang and L. Zu, A three-dimensional thermo-viscoplastic analysis of process-induced residual stress in composite laminates, *Composite structures*, **129**, 2015, pp: 60-69.
- [7] L. Zhu and Y. Xiao, Nonlinear constitutive model for fibre reinforced composites with different properties in tension and compression, *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, **30**, 2013, pp: 184-190.
- [8] J. Wang, Y. Xiao and S.S. Liu, Finite element analysis of elastic-plastic problem for fibre reinforced resin composite with different properties in tension and compression, *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, **32**, 2015, (in press).